

THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN FORMING OUR NATIONAL VALUES

Gaziev Jobirkhon Jurakhonovich

Teacher of Namangan state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10066172>

Annotation: this article provides detailed information about the formation and development of our national pride, national culture and national value to students in the lessons of national values and music culture.

Keywords: national, student, interest, music, culture, student, lesson, art, national value, tradition.

Music lessons for students in higher education institutions should be conducted together with measures for the formation of national values. Because, as a member of society, a person is always under spiritual and educational influences as a representative of various groups and communities. That is, the character, behavior of each person has a positive or negative influence of the nation, people, professional category, community and family to which he belongs. Historical conditions, era, spiritual and educational environment in society and influences on national values are reflected in the outlook, way of thinking and thinking of young people. [1] The teacher should remember that the song is the main educational and educational material of the music lesson when choosing the song repertoire to include in the annual work plan. Therefore, the songs taught to children should be diverse and interesting, distinguished by the fact that they are ideologically and artistically focused on one goal. It should not be forgotten that songs have a powerful effect on the emotions of children, and therefore good songs serve as a powerful tool for educating students in a musical-aesthetic spirit. [2]

It is necessary to include more songs of Uzbek composers in the academic year plan. Because only such songs serve to educate students in an artistic and ideological spirit. In addition, these songs reflect different aspects of nature, children and school life, so they seem very interesting to children.

According to the program, the teacher should choose a song, taking into account the children's singing abilities, taking into account the formation of vocal and choral skills. Children's folklore in the annual work plan songs should also be included. Such songs are national it helps to know our values, traditions, identity.

Also, the annual schedule reflects various holidays and famous dates there must be works. Such songs serve to develop children's ideological and political consciousness. [3]

Children are lively, bold for the future to become mature people who go step by step need That's why it is necessary to achieve more cheerful, lively works in the repertoire. And for the development of children in all aspects, to educate performance skills, performance for the breath to be deep, sincere and emotional

the repertoire includes songs of various types: dramatic, lyrical, sad. [4]

It is also necessary to include cheerful, fast, slow, satirical and humorous songs. In the annual plan, it is appropriate to show the material that will be covered consecutively during the academic year.[5] For example, it is necessary to start the repertoire of a song with a lighter song that corresponds to the theme of the first quarter, and then, depending on the musical maturity of the child, it is necessary to gradually complicate the composition. This structure of the annual plan also makes it easier to divide by quarters. During the year, students should learn 10-12 songs, depending on the simplicity and complexity of the works.

References:

1. Bekmatov S. The art of security. Instructional manual. Tashkent. 2007. - P. 10.
2. Yuldoshev Sh, Usmanov S. Pedagogical technology basics. - Tashkent, - Science, 2001. -P. 42.
3. Tolipov K, Usmonboeva M. Practical foundations of pedagogical technologies. Tashkent "Science" 2006. - P. 61.
4. Fozilov J., Sultanov R., Saidov H. Formation of teacher's spirituality. Tashkent "East" 2000. - P. 54.
5. Kadirov. P. "Singing loudly in elementary school". - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1997.- P.10.